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SUSTAINABLE MUNICIPAL WASTE MANAGEMENT AND GREEN GROWTH - A CASE STUDY OF KANPUR CITY, U.P.

Vandana Dwivedi

ABSTRACT

Effective Municipal waste management is vital for urban sustainability, environmental protection, and public health. This study aims to characterize Kanpur City's current Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) situation and pinpoint the primary barriers in effective MSW management. The suggested framework includes a multi faceted strategy for waste reduction at the source, such as public awareness and education programmes and efficient collection systems. Recycling and circular economy principles play a pivotal role in efficient SWM. Implementation of smart technologies, such as sensor-based waste bins and data analytics, enhances the efficiency of waste collection routes, reducing fuel consumption and associated carbon emissions. Furthermore, community participation and stakeholder collaboration need to be encouraged to develop a sense of shared responsibility for waste management. An exploratory case study design was used in this study to investigate and compare how much Kanpur Municipality's current waste management systems—which are based on citizen awareness and municipal policies, processes, procedures, and practices—are contributing to sustainable waste management.

Introduction

Kanpur is a significant industrial town in Uttar Pradesh, India's northern-most state. This town is situated on the south bank of the River Ganga, 80 km west of Lucknow, the state capital¹. It is Uttar Pradesh's second most populous city, behind Lucknow, and has one of the India's largest urban agglomerations (Britannica 2024)². The city is also renowned as the state's industrial capital. Kanpur's industrialization and strategic location contributed to its enormous prosperity under the British Raj (1858–1947). It was referred to as the Manchester of Asia and was well renowned around the world for producing apparel³. Green growth is supporting economic growth and development in order to guarantee that natural resources continue to provide the resources and environmental services that are vital to our well-being⁴. Green development is a holistic approach to urban planning, infrastructure, and resource management that emphasizes

environmental protection, social equality, and economic sustainability. Diverse definitions of green growth were offered by major international players. Green growth emphasises environmentally sustainable economic growth as a means of advancing low-carbon, socially inclusive development (UNESCAP)⁵.

Solid-waste management is the collection, treatment, and disposal of solid material that is discarded because it has served its purpose or is no longer useful (Britannica)⁶. Improper solid waste management results in soil and water pollution, air pollution, habitat destruction, public health issues, and a negative impact on the overall aesthetics of an area. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach involving community education, improved infrastructure, and effective government policies and regulations. Efficient solid waste management is crucial for environmental sustainability and public health. It includes waste

segregation at source, recycling programmes, composting, waste to energy technologies, landfill management, public awareness and education, extended producer's responsibility, waste audits, collection and transportation efficiency, community engagement, research and innovations, etc.

The increasing volume and complexity of waste associated with the modern economy is posing a serious risk to eco-systems and human health. According to the United Nations Environment Programme Report, Every year, an estimated 11.2 billion tonnes of solid waste is collected worldwide and decay of the organic proportion of solid waste is contributing about 5 per cent of global greenhouse gas emissions⁷. Waste streamline, whether created from residential or industrial sources, is the most pressing issue of our day. The magnitude of the waste stream is determined by the consumer product's life cycle, from manufacture to disposal. And, the way in which our society has manufactured, consumed, and disposed; waste streamlines is going to be a 'waste tsunami' in a few years⁸. U.N. established the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) to build a better and more sustainable future for all by 2030 which included major aspects like sustainability, waste management, product recycling, and environment.

Objectives

1. To explore the status of Kanpur City's municipal solid waste management.
2. To assess the satisfaction levels of the residents of Kanpur city regarding the solid waste management services provided by the Kanpur Municipal Corporation (Kanpur Nagar Nigam).
3. To assess respondent's understanding regarding the problems caused by increased waste generation, irregular collection, and inefficient management in Kanpur City and their impact on public health and urban environment.

Research Methodology

The current research study focused solely on Kanpur city. The research study included both

primary and secondary data. The secondary data of solid waste generation and management was collected from the report given by Kanpur Nagar Nigam, other government reports, online database, etc. The primary data was collected through a self-structured questionnaire. The purpose behind collecting primary data was to assess the respondents' satisfaction regarding solid waste management in Kanpur city by Kanpur Municipal Corporation. The questionnaire comprises questions about solid waste generation, segregation, and disposal. The respondents were the households from Kanpur City.

Four wards were chosen from Kanpur city's total of 110 wards for a detailed study. The criterion behind selection of wards was to select two wards of highest population concentration and two wards of lowest population concentration. Yashoda Nagar and Naubasta wards, with populations of 86,986 and 82,818 respectively, were identified as having the highest population density. The wards with the lowest population concentration were Collectorganj and Bhannana Purwa, which had populations of 15,870 and 13,740, respectively. For the selection of respondents, simple random sampling method was adopted. Thirty households from each ward were chosen for the primary survey. The primary data collection aimed to assess the satisfaction levels of respondents regarding the solid waste management services provided by the Kanpur Municipal Corporation (Kanpur Nagar Nigam). This approach was designed to gather first-hand insights into the effectiveness, efficiency, and overall public perception of waste management practices, including waste collection, transportation, segregation, and disposal. Understanding the satisfaction levels of residents is crucial for identifying service gaps, prioritizing improvements, and ensuring a cleaner, more sustainable urban environment in Kanpur City. The collected responses were interpreted using Microsoft Excel and SPSS software. These tools enabled a comprehensive analysis of the data, ensuring accurate insights into the respondents' satisfaction levels with the solid waste management

services provided by the Kanpur Municipal Corporation.

Status of Solid Waste Management in Kanpur City

Kanpur city has a population of around 27,67,031 and a Municipal area around 261.50 square kilometres, according to the 2011 Census. From 114.55 square kilometres in 1961 to 261.51 square kilometres now, the Municipal area has expanded. The largest and most significant city in

Uttar Pradesh is Kanpur. Administratively, it is divided into six administrative zones and 110 wards, each having an average ward population of 19,000–26,000. The concentration of industry is the main reason for the relatively high density despite the little area of irrigated land. More pressure is placed on the infrastructure services and facilities if they are not updated to meet the demands of the expanding population.

Table 01 : Actual/Projected Population and Solid Waste Generation in Kanpur City.

Years	Actual/Projected Population (In Lakhs)	Growth Rate (In Percentage)	Solid Waste Generation (Metric Tonne)
2012	27.96	0.78	1258.27
2017	29.06	3.93	1307.72
2021	29.97	3.13	1348.68
2025	30.70	2.42	1381.34
2031	31.82	3.65	1431.82
2035	32.59	2.42	1466.50
2041	33.78	3.65	1520.09
2045	34.60	2.42	1556.90

Source: City Sanitation Plan for Kanpur, Report by Administrative Staff College of India, Hyderabad (ASCI) https://kmc.up.nic.in/smartcity/Kanpur%20CSP_%20Final_Report_%202013_RS_ASCl.pdf

Table 01 shows the city's population growth trends throughout time. Since the production of solid waste and population expansion are directly correlated, there is a constant upward tendency in both. The city's estimated solid waste output is expected to

reach 1381.34 MT in 2025 and 1556.90 MT in 2045 due to the growing population and consumerist lifestyle. Kanpur city has quite high rates of poverty, even if there has n't been enough recent study to pin point the exact extent of poverty in the area. Kanpur

Nagar Nigam states that 356 slums in the city have been officially registered. According to DUDA's 2003 study and KNN papers, there are 390 slums in Kanpur overall. 3.68 lakh people, or 14.5% of the total population, were estimated to live in slums according to the 2001 census. In 2006, the KNN estimated that the number of people living in slums was around 5.0 lakh, or 20% of the overall population. The ASCI team calculates that 18% of the population lives in slum regions and the other 82% lives in non-slum areas by

extrapolating the 2001 census data, the KNN estimate from 2006, and the KNN estimate of slum areas in 2011¹⁰.

In urban impoverished regions, there is insufficient home coverage of solid waste management services and general inefficiency in collection, which results in the dumping of solid trash in open spaces and sewers, endangering public health and the environment.

Table 02 : Present Status of Solid Waste Management in Kanpur City

1	Per capita generation of waste in grams	550
2	Total waste collection TPD	1,200
3	No. of wards and percentage of wards practicing sources segregation	No. of wards- 44 % of total Wards 40%
4	Total quantity transported in TPD	Processing Plant-1200 SLF-120 Dumpsites-453
5	Total quantity of existing legacy waste in tones	7,42,931
6	Land occupied by the dump site (acres)	68.39
7	Projected waste generation in 2025 in TPD	1,897.91

Source: Report received from Kanpur Municipal Corporation
TPD- Ton per day, SLF- Secured Landfill Facility, ULBs- Urban Local Bodies

Table 02 exhibits that the solid waste management system in Kanpur City faces significant challenges, as highlighted by the current data. The per capita waste generation stands at 550 grams, contributing to a total daily waste collection of 1,200 TPD (tons per day). Of this, only 40% of the 44 wards practice source segregation, indicating a need for broader awareness and implementation of waste sorting at the household level.

Waste transportation is a major component, with 1,200 TPD sent to processing plants, 120 TPD to sanitary landfill (SLF), and 453 TPD to dumpsites, reflecting a heavy reliance on open dumping. This

approach not only consumes significant land (68.39 acres) but also risks environmental contamination and land degradation. The city also faces a critical issue with 7,42,931 tonnes of existing legacy waste, which demands urgent remediation through techniques like biomining and bio remediation.

Looking ahead, the projected waste generation for 2025 is estimated at 1,897.91 TPD, representing a significant increase that could overwhelm the current waste management infrastructure if not addressed. This growth underscores the need for comprehensive waste reduction strategies, improved source segregation,

expanded recycling capabilities, and effective waste-to-energy solutions to sustainably manage the city's escalating waste burden.

Assessment of The Satisfaction Levels of Respondents Regarding the Solid Waste Management

Solid waste management is a critical component of urban sustainability, directly impacting public health, environmental quality, and the livability of cities. To assess the effectiveness of the Kanpur Municipal Corporation in managing solid waste, data was collected through a structured questionnaire. This survey aimed to evaluate the environmental performance of the corporation, residents' satisfaction levels, and the challenges faced in waste management. Key aspects explored include the success of Kanpur Nagar Nigam on environmental grounds, the ratings provided by residents for its

waste management efforts, the factors contributing to increasing waste, and the problems arising from inefficient collection and poor waste handling. Additionally, the study sought suggestions from respondents for scientific and efficient waste management solutions. The insights gained from this analysis are expected to guide strategic improvements in the city's waste management system, fostering a cleaner and more sustainable urban environment.

The findings based upon responses collected from the respondents reveal varying levels of satisfaction among residents. A significant portion of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the frequency of waste collection, particularly in densely populated areas. Additionally, while some wards demonstrated good practices in waste segregation, others lacked awareness and proper infrastructure.

Table 03 : Rating You Would Give To Kanpur Nagar Nigam for Handling Solid Waste Management

Responses	Frequency	Per cent
Poor	61	50.8%
Good	44	36.7%
Average	14	11.7%
Very Good	1	0.8%
Excellent	0	0%
Total	120	100.0%

All respondents (100%) believe that the Kanpur Municipal Corporation is not successful in the field of solid waste management, indicating a unanimous dissatisfaction with the municipal efforts. The responses clearly indicate that Kanpur Nagar Nigam is not successful in managing solid waste on

environmental grounds. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Half of the respondents (50.8%) rate Kanpur Nagar Nigam's handling of SWM as poor. A significant portion (36.7%) rate it as good, 11.7% as average, and only 0.8% as very good. No respondents rated it

as excellent, reflecting general dissatisfaction but some recognition of efforts made.

In Table 04 to table 06, interpretation is done for the data which was collected through the scaling

method. Four options were given to respondents: most important(1), very important(2), important(3) and least important(4). Clear instructions were given to the respondents to give their preferences 1,2,3,4 to the available options.

Table 04 : Reasons for Increasing Solid Waste in Kanpur City

Reasons	Responses	Frequency	Percentages
Increase in population	Most Important	61	50.8%
	Very Important	58	48.3%
	Important	1	0.8%
	Least Important	0	0%
Improper management of solid waste	Most Important	58	48.3%
	Very Important	60	50.0%
	Important	2	1.7%
	Least Important	0	0%
Rapid urbanization	Most Important	1	0.8%
	Very Important	2	1.7%
	Important	116	96.7%
	Least Important	1	0.8%
Rise in consumerist lifestyle	Most Important	0	0%
	Very Important	0	0%
	Important	1	0.8%
	Least Important	119	99.2%

The data presented in Table 04 reveals the primary factors contributing to the increasing solid waste in Kanpur City based on respondent perceptions. The most significant reason identified is the "Increase in Population," with 50.8% of respondents rating it as Most Important and 48.3% as Very Important, reflecting the direct correlation between population growth and waste generation. This highlights the pressing need for capacity expansion and better planning to accommodate the waste management demands of a rapidly growing urban population.

"Improper Management of Solid Waste" also emerged as a critical concern, with 48.3% considering it Most Important and 50.0% as Very Important. This indicates systemic issues in waste handling, including inefficient collection, poor segregation, and inadequate processing infrastructure, which exacerbate the waste problem. Interestingly, "Rapid Urbanization" was perceived differently, with a majority (96.7%) categorizing it as Important rather than Most Important or Very Important. This suggests that while urbanization contributes to waste generation, it is not seen as an

immediate, high-priority concern by most respondents, possibly reflecting the gradual pace of infrastructure and lifestyle changes in the city.

On the other hand, the "Rise in Consumerist Lifestyle" was overwhelmingly rated as Least Important by 99.2% of the respondents, indicating that the local population perceives this factor as having a minimal direct impact on waste levels, despite its significant contribution to waste in other contexts globally. Overall, the responses indicate a strong awareness of population growth and poor

waste management practices as the primary drivers of increasing solid waste, underscoring the need for systematic improvements in waste collection, segregation, and processing to sustainably manage Kanpur's urban waste challenges.

Table 05 exhibits that disease transmission and an increase in pests like flies and mosquitoes are the most critical problems, with 79.2% and 78.3% respectively marking these as very important. Environmental pollution is considered important by 87.5%, while visual effects are seen as least

Table 05 : Problems Have Arisen in Kanpur Due to Increase in Waste Generation and Irregular Collection & Inefficient Management.

Problems	Responses	Frequency	Percentages
Transmission of diseases	Most Important	24	20.0%
	Very Important	95	79.2%
	Important	1	.8%
	Least Important	0	0%
Increasing water, air and soil pollution	Most Important	0	0%
	Very Important	12	10.0%
	Important	105	87.5%
	Least Important	3	2.5%
Visual effects	Most Important	2	1.7%
	Very Important	0	0%
	Important	13	10.8%
	Least Important	105	87.5%
Increase of flies, moths and mosquitoes, etc	Most Important	94	78.3%

important by 87.5%.

Segregation at the source is the top suggestion, with 65.8% rating it as most important. Wide spread awareness of the 3R concept is also emphasized, with 70.8% considering it very important. Ensuring individual responsibility is mostly rated as important (71.7%). The use of AI in waste management is least prioritized, with 99.2% considering it least important.

Suggestions

There should be more accountability for managing solid waste among the general population and the organizations involved in trash management.

Similarly, the private concessionaire that manages the city's contract must impose steps to carry out the services in accordance with the agreement to reach 100% coverage. Technology plays a crucial role in modernization and enhancement of solid waste management procedures. By adding sensors and RFID technology to garbage bins, fill levels can be tracked in real time. Modern technology uses gasification or incineration to turn trash into electricity. These techniques may provide a more sustainable approach to waste management by assisting in the reduction of trash volume while producing energy. In Kanpur, inclusive growth is impeded by ineffective solid waste management. Therefore, by implementing

Table 07 : Suggestions for Managing Solid Waste in an Efficient and Scientific Way

Practice	Responses	Frequency	Percentages
Segregation at the generated source	Most Important	79	65.8%
	Very Important	34	28.3%
	Important	6	5.0%
	Least Important	1	.8%
Awareness of 3R concept and implementation of this process at a wider level	Most Important	7	5.8%
	Very Important	85	70.8%
	Important	28	23.3%
	Least Important	0	0%
Ensuring responsibility of each and every individual towards solid waste management at administrative and citizens level	Most Important	33	27.5%
	Very Important	1	.8%
	Important	86	71.7%
	Least Important	0	0%
Using the high technology like AI (Artificial Intelligence) in the field of	Most Important	1	.8%

solid waste management based on green development principles, the entire system may be rendered more efficient. The 3R idea (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle) should be widely implemented across the city to assure the achievement of zero waste.

Conclusion

The results of this study show that people's understanding of and responsibility for solid trash management is extremely low. Very little effort is being made to separate garbage, and very few individuals are aware of the need for waste segregation in the city. Even at the level of authority, there was a lack of sense of accountability.

As per report given by Kanpur Nagar Nigam, there is a reported deficiency of 620 safai karmacharis against the requirement of 1400 safai karmacharis translating to a 44% deficit. Zero waste and inclusive green development are hampered by the poor disposal of waste in the city, since most of the garbage is disposed of in landfills without any treatment. Given that the majority of the population in the city lacks SWM awareness as well as the negative effects of current practices that are destroying the environment and public health, efforts need to be done to spread awareness and educate the public.

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